

FLEXURAL FATIGUE STRENGTH OF 3D-PRINTED CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The thermoplastic carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRTP) molded by Mark Two, which is a FDM type 3D printer, can reduce the production cost compared to the conventional molding method in which CFRP sheets are stacked and pressed. That is because it is possible to read 3D data in advance and directly mold finished products. However, CFRTP molded by 3D printer has inferior mechanical properties compared to those molded by the conventional method. In this study, the flexure fatigue test and CT imaging were performed to obtain the knowledge about the decrease in rigidity and internal damage of the CFRTP specimen molded by 3D printer. The size of the test piece is a 240×15×3.0[mm] strip, and an artificial delamination is provided at the center of the test piece with 0[mm], 60[mm], 90[mm] Kapton films interposed. Load control is performed so that the displacement becomes constant at 1.5[mm], the frequency is 1[Hz], and repeats 1×10^4 times. CT imaging was performed before the flexure fatigue test. From these experimental results, it was found that the load-deflection hysteresis loop obtained from the flexure fatigue test showed an elastic change and the mechanical property did not change. In addition, although the stiffness decreased as the separation lengthened, the stiffness of each specimen increased slightly before and after the fatigue test. From CT imaging, it was found that the delamination was strongly adhered.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has superior properties such as toughness, strength, and lightweight compared to conventional metal materials. In addition, CFRP is a laminated material, so it is possible to design it to properties that fit the purpose depending on the method of lamination. Initially, these properties were used in the aerospace field and sporting goods, in recent years, the range of use of CFRP, such as some automobile parts, has gradually expanded. In the future, CFRP seems to occupy an important position as an industrial material to replace metal materials.

However, CFRP has the disadvantage that the production cost tends to be high. For example, the press molding used when molding thermoplastic CFRP (CFRTP) takes about 15 minutes. The Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) method used to mold thermosetting CFRP is about 150 minutes. Autoclave molding, which can expect mechanical properties superior to these two molds, takes about 25 hours. In these molding methods, CFRP sheets are first superposed. Next, placed in a mold and pressed to mold. Finally, after molding, unnecessary portions must be removed. Thus, the process to finish the product is long, and as a result, the production cost tends to be high.

Therefore, research and development of a molding method using an FDM 3D printer [1-2] has been advanced to eliminate this drawback. The product can be molded directly from 3D data using an FDM type 3D printer. The production cost can be suppressed more than conventional methods [3-5].

FDM 3D printer is a printing method widely known at present. The FDM 3D printer is a method in which a semi-liquid thermoplastic resin is ejected from a nozzle and a three-dimensional model is stacked.

Mark Two manufactured by Markforged used in this laboratory is a FDM 3D printer that can

laminate thermoplastic resin and carbon fiber independently. The CFRTP molded by Mark One earlier than this has been subjected to tensile tests, flexure tests, compression tests, impact tests, etc, by various people in the past [10-15]. However, there are few reports of fatigue tests on CFRTP specimens molded by Mark Two, and it is urgent to obtain knowledge on their durability.

CFRTP products molded by 3D printer have inferior mechanical properties for use in high performance applications than CFRTP products molded by conventional molding methods. In this research, too, the three-point flexure test and the fatigue test of the test piece molded by the autoclave and the test piece molded by the 3D printer were conducted, and the rigidity of the test piece molded by the 3D printer was lower than that of the test piece molded by the autoclave. It was confirmed. This is because the carbon content of test pieces molded by a 3D printer is about 30%, that of an autoclave molded carbon is 60%, and such material properties are possessed. For this reason, research is also underway to improve the mechanical properties of CFRP products molded with 3D printers.

In this study, fatigue tests are performed on test pieces molded by FDM 3D printer. In addition, by performing CT scan, internal damage in the test piece is visually investigated, and it is decided to obtain knowledge on deterioration of bending stiffness and internal damage of 3D printer formed CFRTP.

2 TEST PIECES

The test pieces used in this study are shown in Fig.1. The dimensions of the test piece are 240×18×3.0[mm], and it is a 24 ply UD material with a stacking direction of 0°, and it was molded with Markforged Mark Two installed in this laboratory. Fig.2 shows Mark Two manufactured by Markforged.

During the molding of the test piece, the operation was temporarily stopped, and a Kapton film was held in the center of the test piece to provide an artificial delamination. There are three types of delamination length: 0[mm], 60[mm] and 120[mm]. Fig.3 shows the completed test piece.

Four nylon layers are attached to the bottom of this test piece. There are two reasons for attaching this. The first reason is that if the layers of nylon and carbon fiber are separated, the test pieces will be distorted due to thermal contraction. The second reason is that it is possible to peel off this nylon after molding, but the carbon fiber is also peeled off, and it is thought that this will change the material properties of the test pieces.

Fig.1 Test pieces made by “Mark Two”

Fig.2 Markforged's FDM 3D printer
“Mark Two”

3.Experimental Producer

In this study, the following tests were conducted.

3.1 CT Scan

We perform a CT scan to compare the internal damage of the specimen before and after the test.

3.2 Three Point Flexure Test

To compare and investigate the decrease in stiffness of the test specimen due to the fatigue test, we perform a static 3-point flexure test using a load-controlled universal tester (made by MTS) as shown in Fig.4. The jigs were designed according to JIS K 7017 for this test. The jig speed is 32[mm/min], and the distance between fulcrums is 200[mm]. Load and displacement data will be collected if bending is made to around 2[mm].

3.3 Three Point Flexure Fatigue Test

We perform a three-point flexure fatigue test with reference to the results in 2. The jig used until then was used in the 3-point flexure test. The load frequency was 1[Hz], so the influence of heat generation was to be small. The repeat count was 1×10^4 times. The displacement was around 1.5[mm]. Therefore, the load given to each test piece is 58 N for the delamination length 0 mm, 58[N] for the delamination length 60[mm], and 50[N] for the delamination length 120[mm].

Fig.3 The load control type universal testing machine
(manufactured by MTS Co., Ltd.)

• 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Three-Point Flexure Test Results

Fig. 4 shows the results of the three-point bending test. The result before the flexure fatigue test is a solid line, the result after the fatigue test is a broken line. From this result, the rigidity is lower for longer separation. It can be seen that the rigidity of the test piece is increased before and after the test. It is considered that this is because the separated part was in close contact in the fatigue test.

Fig.4 Three-point flexure test result

4.2 Three-Point Fatigue Test Results

Fig. 5 shows the hysteresis loop obtained from the flexure fatigue test. The first cycle is a solid line, the 10000th cycle is a broken line.

From these results, it can be seen that the hysteresis loop changes elastically in each test piece. Therefore, it is considered that it is not enough to change the property of the specimen if the displacement is 1.5[mm] and the number of repetitions is 1×10^4 times. In addition, it can be seen that the slope of the hysteresis loop decreases as the separation lengths.

From this result, it is considered that even larger load displacement and number of repetitions are required to cause internal damage to the test piece.

Fig.5 The hysteresis loop of each test piece

4.3 CT mage investigation

Fig.6 to 8 show CT images of each test piece before the experiment. These CT images was at the end of the separation. From the top view of the test piece, the center of the test piece is white. Also, from the cross-sectional view, it can be confirmed that the upper part is warped from the delamination of the test piece. This is because the film is warped due to heat shrinkage when molding with a 3D printer. As a result, the center of the test piece is in close contact. The black part is a void, and the void on the line can be identified from the cross-sectional view of the test piece and the view from the top. This is a void between fibers generated during lamination.

In addition, from the results of static three-point bending test and the results of fatigue test, it was considered that internal damage did not occur in the test piece, and it was judged that the inside of the test piece did not change significantly with these CT images. Therefore, CT images after the test was not performed.

Fig.6 CT image of no delamination

Fig.7 CT image of 60mm delamination

Fig.8 CT image of 90mm delamination

• 5. CONCLUSION

The following was found from this study

1. From the result of the flexure test, the rigidity slightly increased.
2. The longer the delamination, the lower the rigidity.
3. Hysteresis loop obtained by the flexure fatigue test shows elastic change, mechanical property has not changed.
4. From the CT image investigation before the test, the center part of the separation is in close contact, and it is not sufficient as an artificial interlayer separation.

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